

Types, stages and forms of extracurricular activities

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Аннотация: В данной научной статье рассказывается об организации внеурочной деятельности, ее видах, этапах и формах, а также об организации интересных игр для учащихся во внеурочное время.

Ключевые слова: Основные формы внеурочной деятельности, система классных занятий, сборник, понятие, речевой этикет.

Abstract: This scientific article talks about the organization of extracurricular activities, their types, stages and forms, as well as the organization of interesting games for students outside of class

Key words: The main forms of extracurricular activities, class lesson system, collection, concept, speech etiquette.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada sinfdan tashqari ishlarni tashkil qilish, ularning turlari, bosqichlari va shakllari hamda o'quvchilarni dars mashg'ulotlaridan tashqari vaqtda qiziqarli o'yinlarni tashkil qilish haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sinfdan tashqari ishlarning asosiy shakllari, sinf dars tizimi, kolleksiya to'plash, konsepsiya, nutq odobi.

Extracurricular activities are a component of the educational work of a general secondary school, one of the forms of organizing students' free time. Extracurricular activities provide ample opportunities to shape students as well-rounded individuals and prepare them for life. Extracurricular activities include a system of various activities conducted with students and aimed at educating and

educating them. Such trainings are organized by the pedagogical team, class leader, leadership of youth organizations and children's self-management organizations outside of school hours. Students' palaces, young technicians, young naturalists, young hikers' club and other extracurricular institutions provide great support in the organization of students' extracurricular activities. The main forms of extracurricular work are public work (events in school clubs, parties, debates and contests, organization of quizzes and exhibitions, excursions to nature, schools and museums), club work (participation of students in various clubs, sports sections, ensembles), independent it is possible to show works (students' extracurricular studies, collecting collections, independent engagement in technology, music, visual arts, drawing, etc.).

Activities that are carried out together with students outside the classroom, but on the territory of the school, are called extracurricular activities. Almost all teachers are involved in extracurricular activities and use it as an important tool for comprehensive development of the student. Extracurricular activities differ from activities in their own characteristics.

This work has a voluntary character, students participate in various clubs depending on their interests and abilities, and participate in family and individual activities held outside of school at their own request. There are different types and forms of extracurricular activities, and every school is required to involve all students in this activity without exception. The content and form of extracurricular activities depends on the interests, requirements and personal preferences of students and local conditions. In 1994, the Ministry of Public Education of Uzbekistan issued the "Concepts of educational work outside the classroom" in the organization of educational work according to the requirements, especially giving independence to students was emphasized. One of the main tasks of extracurricular

activities is to make the life of students enjoyable, meaningful and cultural, to teach them to live and work as a team.

Forms of extracurricular and extracurricular activities:

- a) methods of oral work (political information, meetings, gatherings, lectures, documents, debates, meetings, question-and-answer evenings, debates, etc.);
- b) practical methods of work: cultpokhods, excursions, spartakiades, Olympiads, contests and work with student activists, green patrols, technical creativity, young technicians' circles, sabbaticals, etc.;
- c) methods of exhibition work: school museums, gallery of war and labor heroes, tools of artistic creativity, organizational stands, etc.

There are the following types of extracurricular activities, which are divided into:

- Public affairs-related to the political-enlightenment work carried out among students, current issues of internal and foreign policy, political information, interviews, documents, lectures: (September 1, March 8, 9 - May, October 1, March 21, etc.) literary and artistic gatherings.
- Cultural and public events: -literary evenings, performances, artistic amateur evenings, debates of sharp wits, etc.
- Group work: In this case, the teacher can conduct educational work and activities with a certain group of students outside the classroom.
- Individual work: in this case, the teacher or educator works according to the individual age characteristics of the student. For example: shy, passive students can be found in every class.

The following educational activities take an important place in extracurricular activities:

- a) political information;

- b) meetings of students with industrial leaders and famous people;
- c) scientific circles;
- g) clubs, country study clubs, special clubs, physical, cultural sports clubs, school activities, extracurricular reading, etc.

The purpose of extracurricular activities is to improve the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in native language classes, to familiarize with the concepts of native language such as phonetics, grammar, morphemics, syntax, word combinations, words, and sentences, to regularly instill love for native language. is to raise a conscious perfect person who can shoot and apply it in practice. Extracurricular activities are closely related to the curriculum and closely support the implementation of the goals and tasks provided for in it. For this, it is required to raise the level of inquisitiveness and creativity in students. Since 1959, special extracurricular classes have been organized in schools. Extracurricular activities are held once a week in the 1st-2nd grade, and once every 2 weeks in the 3rd-4th grade. In the process of teaching literacy, 17-20 minutes of the last alphabet lesson of the week are allocated. The main purpose of extracurricular activities in elementary grades is to develop students' interest in science, to form knowledge, skills and abilities in the native language that complement and deepen the knowledge acquired in the lesson. In elementary grades, "extracurricular work" in the native language refers to voluntary activities based on the principle of discretion based on the material related to the program, organized by the students under the guidance of the teacher. Two types of extracurricular activities can be distinguished. The first type involves working with children who are lagging behind in mastering planned materials, and the second type includes activities with children who are interested in learning their mother tongue. It is known that the first type of training is currently available in all countries of our country.

Out-of-school activities consist of educational and cultural activities organized by specially organized institutions. The role of extra-curricular children's educational institutions in the education of children is extremely important, and such institutions can be divided into 2 types:

1. Children's educational institutions with a wide profile, i.e., carrying out a variety of educational and cultural education activities (school houses, palaces, children's clubs, children's sectors at cultural houses, children's playgrounds, summer holiday camps and more.
2. Narrow-profile children's educational and educational institutions - that is, institutions that carry out educational and cultural education work with children in a certain field: (children's libraries, young naturalists, children's theaters, children's creative houses, children's tourism, excursions, children's puppet theaters, children's railways, children's stadiums, sports fields, music schools, etc.

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